

**DEVELOPMENT OF AN APIARY AGRIBUSINESS MODEL FOR TRAINING
UNDERGRADUATE AGRICULTURAL EDUCATION STUDENTS IN UNIVERSITIES IN
NORTH-EASTERN, NIGERIA**

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Abstract

The aim of the study was to develop an apiary agribusiness model for training undergraduate agricultural education students in northeast Nigeria. The study answered three research questions and reviewed relevant literature related to the research questions. The study adopted two research designs: research and development (R&D) and descriptive survey research designs. The area of the study was the Northeast, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised of forty-one (41) Agricultural Education lecturers in Federal University offering Agricultural Education in Northeast, Nigeria. The entire population (Census) was used for the study. Three research questions were answered. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled: Apiary Agribusiness Training Model for Undergraduate Students questionnaire (AATMUSQ). Apiary Beehive Model along with traditional (Wood Log) hives were constructed by the researcher and tested for quality and quantity of liquid honey, honey comb and wax production. The data were collected by the researcher with the help of five (5) trained research assistants. The data were analysed using mean, standard deviation and inter-rater reliability to answer the research questions. The reliability yielded a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.87, indicating a high reliability. The findings of the study revealed among others that agricultural education students of universities need apiary agribusiness. It was concluded that apiary agribusiness will ensure empowerment of undergraduate agricultural education students after graduation. The study recommended that apiary agribusiness model should be incorporated into the Agricultural Education Curriculum as an entrepreneurship venture for undergraduate agricultural education students in the universities.

Keywords: Agribusiness, Apiary, Education, Model

Introduction

Entrepreneurship otherwise known as Agribusiness in agriculture deals with business of agricultural production which engulfs all spheres of Agriculture including crop production, animal production, agrochemicals, farming as well as apiary just to mention but a few (Maderson, 2023; Tabe-Ojong, 2023). In area of agriculture, apiary is one of the lucrative agribusiness. Apiary which is the most widespread agricultural practices is the care and management of honey bees for the production of honey and wax. Martinez-Lopez *et al.* (2022) opined that apiary business increase honey production, assured sustainable environment, create job opportunities, provide source of raw material to the industries, provide income to individual and nation at large and improve food security. Apiary agribusiness is undertaken in many parts of the world such as Asia, United States of America, China and Africa

because it serves as a source of food, employment, income generation and the most lucrative enterprise (Rant, 2011). Consequently, there is a compelling need to encourage the apiary agribusiness in the country.

Despite the laudable objectives of apiary agribusiness of providing an opportunity for the production of food, source of raw material to industries, income generation and improvement of standard of living (FGN, 2018), it has not been captured in the curriculum of agricultural education in Nigerian Universities, hence students graduate without knowledge, skills and competencies for apiary business.

The integration of apiary into the curriculum of undergraduate agricultural education is expected to provide training to students on effective beekeeping for self-reliance. The introduction will provide the students with more sustainable economic empowerment by providing them with skills for production and marketing of honey and wax in Nigeria and skills for more entrepreneurial venture in agriculture. It has consistently been debated upon that for developing nations, like Nigeria to grow and develop, there is the urgent need for a viable economic programme that can promote growth of small and medium scale enterprises, wealth creation, enhance value re-orientation, mindset, preserve the ecosystem from abuse, create employment opportunities and in the final analysis, achieve sustainable economic development (Saidu et al., 2017; Saidu et al., 2022). Therefore, introduction of modern apiary agribusiness into the curriculum of agricultural education programme that would add value to production of honey and creating job opportunities amongst our teeming youths is inevitable.

Consequently, there is a need to develop and trial test an apiary model to be integrated into the curriculum of undergraduate agricultural education curriculum. Training model development is the multi-step process of creating and improving a course taught at a school or university (Glatthorn et al., 2019). The author added that model development process can be categorized into five basic steps: 1) needs assessment, 2) the planning session, 3) content development, 4) pilot delivery and revision, and 5) the completed curriculum package. According to Alade (2020), for any policy action on integrating a training model into curriculum, such model must be developed by expert(s), tested, effective and accepted. The assertion prompted the researcher to develop a model for training undergraduate agricultural education students in apiary in Federal Universities in North-East Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the laudable objectives of apiary agribusiness of providing an opportunity for the production of food, source of raw material to industries, income generation and improvement of standard of living (FGN, 2018), it has not been captured in the curriculum of agricultural education in Nigerian Universities, hence students graduate without knowledge, skills and competencies for apiary business.

The study conducted by Ibrahim (2017) disclosed that, the persistent increase of unemployment in Nigeria is lack of integrating technical and vocational skills in the curriculum of Nigerian universities. It is as a result that the researcher developed a model beehive for teaching apiary agribusiness for self-reliance of undergraduate agricultural education students in North-east, Nigeria.

Research Questions

- i. What are the needs for training undergraduate agricultural education students in apiary agribusiness in Federal Universities in North-east Nigeria?

- ii. What are the content areas to be integrated into the apiary agribusiness for training undergraduate agricultural education students in Federal Universities in North-east Nigeria?
- iii. What are the procedures for the construction of model beehives for training undergraduate agricultural education students in apiary agribusiness in Federal Universities in North-east Nigeria?

Methodology

The study adopted Research and Development (R&D) in conjunction with descriptive survey research design. The study was conducted in North-Eastern, Nigeria. The population for this study comprised of all 41 agricultural education lecturers. There was no sampling for the study because the number of the population is manageable. Questionnaire was used as an instrument for data collection (Apiary Agribusiness Training Model for Undergraduate Students questionnaire (AATMUSQ). It consisted of sections A and B. Section A consisted of 26 items generated from the literature reviewed. The mode of response consisted of a 4-point rating scale. (AATMUSQ) was face and content validated by five experts. The comments and suggestions of the experts on the suitability, clarity and scope of the content were incorporated in building the final draft of the instrument. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions.

In the construction and development phase, the researcher along with assistants identified suitable materials for the construction of the model beehives, took dimensions and measurement of the constructed beehive as well as traditional bee hives, developed the skeletal structure of beehives, construction of the beehives. The construction of the apiary modern beehives was carried out in the construction workshop of the department of vocational and technology education, faculty of technology education in Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Bauchi.

Results

Research question 1: What are the needs for training undergraduate agricultural education students in apiary agribusiness in Federal Universities in North-east Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Responses of Agricultural Educators on the Need for Apiary Agribusiness Model for Training Undergraduate Agricultural Education Students

S/No.	Questionnaire Items	Mean	Std.	Remark
1.	Apiary agribusiness is needed for honey production	3.90	.31	Highly Needed
2.	Apiary agribusiness is needed for youth empowerment	3.90	.35	Highly Needed
3.	Apiary agribusiness is needed for honey production	3.40	.94	Needed
4.	Train students to be entrepreneurs in apiary agribusiness	3.33	.88	Needed
5.	Make students appreciate the value of apiary agribusiness	3.83	.53	Highly Needed
6.	Encourage students to develop interest in apiary agribusiness	3.65	.66	Highly Needed
7.	Give students practical skills in apiary agribusiness	3.32	1.08	Needed
8.	Train students on construction of assorted beehives (local and modern)	3.72	.58	Highly Needed
9.	Help students to identify correct beehive construction materials	3.60	.64	Highly Needed
10.	Train students on how to manage apiary.	3.43	.77	Needed

11.	Train students how to control swarming in bee colonies	3.52	.68	Highly Needed
12.	Train students how to control robbing among bee colonies	3.78	.52	Highly Needed
13.	Train students how to replace lost queen in bee colony	3.52	.77	Highly Needed
14.	Train students on how to harvest bee products (honey, propolis, pollen, bee wax and royal jelly)	3.60	.64	Highly Needed
15.	Train students on how to process bee products	3.70	.62	Highly Needed
16.	Train students on disease control in apiary	3.47	.68	Needed
17.	Train to perform basic customer care tasks	3.67	.63	Highly Needed
18.	Generate and keep basic financial records	3.48	.68	Needed
	Grand Mean	3.60		Needed

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Result in Table 1 shows the mean response and standard deviation of the need for apiary agribusiness model for training undergraduate agricultural education students. The Table revealed that all the items had their mean values ranged from 3.32 – 3.90 and were above the cut-off point of mean 2.50 indicating that all the items were agreed by the respondents as there is need for apiary agribusiness model for training undergraduate agricultural education students in Federal Universities in North-east Nigeria. The table further revealed that the standard deviation of all the 18 items ranged from 0.31 – 1.08 which imply that there was less variability in the opinion of the respondents.

Research question 2: What are the content areas to be integrated into the apiary agribusiness for training undergraduate agricultural education students in Federal Universities in North-east Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Responses of Agricultural Educators on the Content Areas of Apiary Agribusiness Model for Training Undergraduate Agricultural Education Students

S/No.	Questionnaire Items	Mean	Std.	Remark
1.	Concept of apiary agribusiness	3.70	.59	Highly Required
2.	Apiary site selection	3.77	.59	Highly Required
3.	Construction of beehives	3.70	.60	Highly Required
4.	Materials for construction of beehives	3.68	.65	Highly Required
5.	Techniques of bee attraction (Hiving of apiary)	3.68	.59	Highly Required
6.	Bee as a social insect	3.60	.46	Highly Required
7.	Biology of honey bee	3.77	.56	Highly Required
8.	Management of bee colony	3.77	.57	Highly Required
9.	Economic importance of bees	3.55	.83	Highly Required
10.	Queen/Stock raising in bee keeping	3.32	.72	Required
11.	Honey production and harvesting	3.50	.61	Highly Required

12.	Processing, preservation and marketing of bee	3.73	.57	Highly Required
13.	Hive products and uses	3.68	.59	Highly Required
14.	Diseases and pests of bee	3.70	.59	Highly Required
15.	Bee keeping in schools	3.77	.60	Highly Required
	Grand Mean	3.66		Highly Required

Source: Field Survey, 2021

(N=41)

Results in Table 2 shows the mean response and standard deviation on the content areas of apiary agribusiness model for training undergraduate agricultural education students. The table revealed that all the items had their mean values ranged from 3.32 – 3.77 and were above the cut-off point of mean 2.50 indicating that all the items were accepted by the respondents as content areas of apiary agribusiness model for training undergraduate agricultural education students. The table further revealed that the standard deviation of all the 15 items ranged from 0.46 – 0.72 which imply that there was less variability in the opinion of the respondents.

Research question 3: What are the procedures for the construction of model beehives for training undergraduate agricultural education students in apiary agribusiness in Federal Universities in North-east Nigeria?

In answering this research question, the following procedures or processes were followed by the researcher in developing the model beehive:

1. Review of principles of beehives
2. Review of various types of beehives
3. Review models for developing training manuals
4. Development of the draft version of modern beehives for training of undergraduate agricultural education students in apiary agribusiness
5. Construction of modern beehives for training of undergraduate agricultural education students in apiary agribusiness in accordance with the principles of beehives

Construction Procedure of the Modern Beehive

Step 1

Figure 1: Dimension of the Constructed Beehive

Step 2

Figure 2: Width and top bar of the beehive

Step 3

Figure 3: Skeletal Structure of the Beehive

Step 4

Figure 4: Sealing of the constructed beehive with the top bars

Step 5

Figure 5: Roofing structure of the beehive

Step 6

Figure 6: Constructed beehive

Findings of the Study

The following are the findings arising from this study;

- i. Undergraduate agricultural education students in Federal Universities in North-east Nigeria need training in apiary agribusiness.
- ii. The respondents strongly agreed on the content areas of apiary agribusiness model for training undergraduate agricultural education students in Federal Universities in North-east Nigeria.
- iii. Procedure for the construction of modern beehives for training of undergraduate agricultural education students in apiary agribusiness in Federal Universities in North-east Nigeria has been identified.

Conclusion

Development of apiary agribusiness model for training undergraduate agricultural education students helps and enhances production of pure honey and hive products, ensured sources of raw materials to the industries and can ensure empowerment of undergraduate agricultural education students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Universities should be encouraged to utilize the developed agribusiness model in teaching beekeeping among undergraduate agricultural education students.
2. Government, educational institution and stakeholders should encourage the use of agribusiness model in teaching beekeeping among undergraduate agricultural education students for effective production of pure honey for national food security.
3. The developed modern bee hives is recommended for use by local farmers in order to improve their production capacity in terms of quality and quantity.

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